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Evaluating the Potential of ChatGPT to Support Climate Risk and Adaptation Assessment

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ABSTRACT

Adaptation to climate change is increasingly urgent, as efforts to curb greenhouse gas emissions falter. Scaling up adaptation finance is essential to address climate risks, but no adaptation inventory covers all sectors and regions globally, especially for vulnerable, information-scarce communities. Large language models (LLMs) like ChatGPT could help bridge these gaps through rapid scoping of climate risks, adaptation options, programme costs and potential maladaptation. This paper uses structured conversations with ChatGPT to explore adaptations to climate hazards in the United Kingdom (for a national perspective), Bangladesh (for an education sector) and Ghana (for vulnerable communities). Queries were run multiple times to test consistency of outputs and contextual awareness. Early results are promising when compared with published information and expert insight. Nonetheless, practical steps can be taken for more effective use of LLMs, and these are captured in a checklist for users. Further research is needed to compare ChatGPT with other LLMs in giving reliable, domain-specific information about climate risks and priority adaptations.

1 | Introduction

Adaptation to climate change is becoming more urgent as global efforts to curb emissions of greenhouse gases falter. Although the amount of global adaptation finance doubled between 2018 and 2022, it was only a fraction of the investment in mitigation. In 2021/2022, \$68 billion was allocated to adaptation, whilst \$1171 billion flowed into mitigation projects (Climate Policy Initiative 2024). This compares with an estimated global annual adaptation need of \$212 billion just for emerging markets and developing economies in 2024–2030. Hence, there is a significant adaptation gap between the present levels of demand and investment, with most of this (largely public finance) flowing into water and wastewater projects. Part of the difficulty in accessing finance stems from high debt burdens and stretched budgets; another

challenge is in accurately tracking adaptation finance. The gap can also be explained by the limited attention to adaptation opportunities and benefits aside from a few sectors like agriculture and water. Efforts are further hampered by lack of context-specific information about climate risks and exposures, as well as by low capacities to undertake climate risk and adaptation assessments (CRAs)—especially in some of the most climate-vulnerable countries (Malik and Ford 2024).

Adaptation investment planning typically proceeds in several distinct stages, guided by a climate risk and adaptation framework (Figure 1). Earlier steps are about (1) aligning potential investments with national and sector development goals; (2) gathering and reviewing contextual information; and (3) evaluating potential climate risks and impacts on project elements. This

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FIGURE 1 | An example framework for evaluating climate risks and adaptation options. *Source:* ADB (2023).

third part of the workflow normally involves the analysis of climate model information to assess direct or indirect impacts. For instance, a national adaptation plan might set the high-level goal of improving the climate resilience of surface and groundwater resources to climate change. Long-term hydromet data may uncover falling trends in river flows and groundwater levels that are exacerbated by more erratic seasonal rainfall, more severe storms and higher rates of evaporation. More frequent floods and droughts may, in turn, damage infrastructure and undermine water security.

The work of the analyst subsequently involves (4) compiling a portfolio of adaptation options; (5) appraising and implementing preferred options; and then (6) monitoring, evaluating and reporting adaptation processes or outcomes via a range of indicators (Figure 1). Steps 4 and 5 can be very time-consuming and resource intense activities, even for experienced practitioners. This is because the information needed to complete these tasks is typically dispersed over a wide variety of sources such as government and agency portals, peer-reviewed and grey literature, assorted media outlets and qualitative and quantitative data archives. Moreover, to qualify for adaptation finance, the analyst must establish that the proposed project outputs are designed specifically to address identified climate risks and impacts. Such tasks can involve a considerable amount of time for evidence gathering, especially if the analyst is unfamiliar with the project area(s) and/or sector(s) covered.

As with other areas of science, engineering and medicine, there is growing recognition of the scope for assistive technologies—like Artificial Intelligence (AI) with Machine Learning—to support weather and climate services (Mehryar et al. 2024; UNFCCC 2024). For example, AI is already contributing to improved climate literacy, likelihood estimation for extreme weather events and parameterisation of climate models (e.g. Atkins et al. 2024; Matera et al. 2024; Schneider et al. 2024). AI-based weather models like GraphCast, Pangu-Weather and FengWu are revolutionising medium-range weather forecasting (Lam et al. 2023;

He and Chan 2025) as well as hazard and early warning systems (Filho et al. 2022; Huntingford et al. 2019; Zennaro et al. 2021). Other climate-related uses include rapid image processing of icebergs and deforestation, improved waste management, pollution control and disaster prediction (Masterson 2024). The potential for AI to scale-up data-driven and digital technologies for adaptation is also starting to be realised (World Economic Forum 2024). Meanwhile, researchers and educators are rapidly devising new policies and practices to safeguard academic integrity, whilst also exploring the capabilities of AI for learning, curriculum and career development (Day et al. 2025; Wilby and Esson 2024).

Large language models (LLMs) like ChatGPT (OpenAI), Claude (Anthropic), DeepSeek and Gemini (Google) are AI systems designed to understand and generate human-like text. This branch of AI is distinct from the numerical forecasting tools mentioned above because LLMs are concerned with modelling relationships between words, phrases and sentences based on context. They are pre-trained on massive data sets in order to perform a range of tasks including language processing for synopsis, translation and answering questions (Wang et al. 2025). Development of LLMs is enabled by the surge in online data sources (needed for training), advances in the computational power (needed to run complex neural networks) and innovations in algorithms (needed to support parallel computing and prediction of successive words). Due to their versatility, LLMs have been adopted in fields as diverse as software engineering, biomedical applications, financial trading and education. However, LLMs can generate confident but incorrect or nonsensical information, or reinforce biases present in their training data (Sun et al. 2024). Such limitations can be addressed through fine-tuning, retrieval-augmented generation and human feedback—practices that augment the LLM query by incorporating more context, relevant/up-to-date information or external knowledge. This capability is enabled in the online version of ChatGPT, for instance.

Although LLMs have been used to evaluate climate policy (Salekpay et al. 2024), so far, there have been no applications of the technology to climate adaptation options analysis. This paper provides a first look at the potential for ChatGPT to support climate action through CRAs. ChatGPT was chosen because it is the Generative AI most widely used by organisations (AI at Wharton and GBK Collective 2024). The target audience spans new to experienced climate researcher-practitioners who are interested in elucidating climate risks and adaptation measures in various contexts. This might include preliminary scoping for adaptation projects or improving due diligence by expanding risk and option sets beyond what might reasonably be expected from individual experts or teams of professionals. However, it is stressed that the LLM is applied here as an assistive technology, not as a replacement for expert human judgement—especially in high-risk decision-making situations. This echoes the view held by others, such as when used in clinical risk assessment (Heston and Lewis 2024) or as a source of public safety advice (Oviedo-Trespalacios et al. 2023).

The following section sets the scene by summarising conventional approaches to CRAs, which are often ad hoc and labour intensive. The potential of ChatGPT is introduced next along with some cautionary remarks and perspectives from previous

evaluations of this LLM. The practical benefits of deploying ChatGPT as an assistive technology are then illustrated using climate risk and adaptation case studies at national, sector and community scales. The concluding section offers practical tips on implementing LLMs to streamline climate risk assessment and adaptation investments, thereby contributing to a narrowing of the adaptation gap.

2 | Conventional Approaches to Adaptation Options' Identification

According to the joint Multilateral Development Bank methodology, three conditions must be fulfilled by a project to qualify for adaptation finance (European Investment Bank 2022). The project proposal must:

- Step 1: Set out the context of climate change vulnerability.
- Step 2: Make an explicit statement of intent of the project to reduce the climate change vulnerabilities identified.
- Step 3: Articulate a clear and direct link between specific project activities and the climate change vulnerability identified in Step 1.

Three types of activity may be financed (European Investment Bank 2022, 6). Type 1 activities use incremental adaptations to manage physical climate risks and ensure that intended investment objectives are realised despite these risks—for example, increasing the capacity of a drainage channel to cope with larger floods. Type 2 activities directly reduce physical climate risk and develop the adaptive capacity of the system within which the activity takes place—for instance, diversification of a city water supply to cope with both a growing population and more frequent droughts. Type 3 activities address the underlying causes of vulnerability to climate change at the systemic level and/or remove knowledge, capacity, technological and other barriers to adaptation—for example, research and development of new rice varieties that are more resilient to extreme temperatures.

The next step is to find adaptation options that directly address identified climate change vulnerabilities. Conventional wisdom says that adaptation is largely about 'learning by doing' (Kato and Ahem 2008). It is also widely recognised that climate vulnerability is socially, economically and geographically differentiated (Thomas et al. 2019). These two axioms imply that robust adaptation will be iterative (to contend with uncertain projections) whilst tailored to specific contexts (to reflect local variations in climate risk exposure) (Wilby and Dessai 2010). Hence, there is not a globally applicable 'master list' of adaptation options; the best we can hope for is a typology of adaptation actions (Figure 2). These help to organise sets of activities around building human and social resilience; strengthening institutions and governance; deploying information gathering and communication tools; constructing/retrofitting grey and green infrastructure; using financial safety nets and instruments; and implementing new technologies in hazard forecasting and natural resource management. Such adaptation types can be used to guide portfolios of options—for instance, for managing the risk of urban flash floods under climate variability and change (Figure 2).

This sounds straightforward, but some may be wondering about where to source inventories of adaptation options that are relevant to projects in very diverse sectoral and geographic contexts. Fortunately, there are many resources to get started. These include:

- *Archives* of previously financed climate adaptation projects (e.g. Asian Development Bank projects and tenders archive).
- *Indigenous knowledge* such as local rainfall forecasting based on folk lore and observations of the natural world (e.g. Paparrizos et al. 2023).
- *National strategies*, regional development and sector plans (e.g. submitted National Adaptation Plans from developing country Parties)
- *On-line portals* with project-level content that is searchable by climate impact, sector and types of adaptation measure (e.g. EU Climate ADAPT).
- *Peer-reviewed research* into local, systems-level and long-lived adaptations (e.g. Chen et al. 2016; de Bruin et al. 2009; Duc et al. 2017; Ranger et al. 2013; Wilby et al. 2011).
- *Peer-to-peer networks* for sharing examples of good adaptation practice amongst members (e.g. C40 Knowledge Hub for cities).
- *Sector-specific guidance* such as on the incorporation of climate change safety margins in detailed engineering designs (e.g. UK Government climate change allowances for flood risk assessments).
- *Syntheses* of adaptation actions compiled from programmes such as the Global Environment Facility (e.g. Biagini et al. 2014).

Unfortunately, as can be seen from the above list, information about adaptation actions is spread across many sources. Hence, any tool that can consolidate existing option sets and suggest actions for under-represented sectors and places would help to streamline CRAs. Such tasks are well suited for LLMs which are designed to analyse and interpret vast amounts of information plus communicate information in ways that are accessible to non-specialists (Biswas 2023). The following section introduces ChatGPT as a 'helpful assistant' for seeking out adaptation actions that address identified climate risks and vulnerabilities.

3 | Using ChatGPT as a Climate Risk and Adaptation Assistant

The pros and cons of ChatGPT have been discussed in detail elsewhere (see Day 2023; Ray 2023). In short, the main strengths are immediacy of answers and ability to synthesise, edit, create new resources, support coding, simplify complex ideas and support decision-making. The main weaknesses are limits to contextual awareness, plus potential for outdated, biased, harmful or factually inaccurate output (Sun et al. 2024). ChatGPT also does not have knowledge of events, developments or changes beyond the dates of the training data (unless online retrieval is enabled). Moreover, identical prompts by different and even the same user can generate divergent answers. Accuracy has improved as the

FIGURE 2 | An adaptation typology with options to manage risks from urban flooding. Modified from Biagini et al. (2014).

complexity and size of the underlying architecture has grown from 175 billion parameters (GPT-3.5) to around 1 trillion parameters (GPT-4). However, this comes with high environmental costs in terms of energy and water demand, plus associated carbon emissions (d'Aramon et al. 2024; Digital Humanities Climate Coalition 2024).

The following sections are based on 'conversations' between ChatGPT and the author about climate risks and adaptations at various scales. Prompts were designed to explore how far ChatGPT could contextualise and prescribe financeable adaptation options for identified climate risks. Unfortunately, the exact training techniques and data used to build GPT-4o are not publicly available. However, according to ChatGPT, *The most recent data used to train GPT-4o extends up to June 2024... [and it] can retrieve and process up-to-date information from the web when necessary, further improving its responses to recent developments.*

To maximise the uptake of findings from this research, the free, globally available version of GPT-4o was used with default settings (in May–June 2025). These conditions include a temperature parameter of 1.0 which means that there is some randomness in the responses. This is considered desirable as a broader ensemble of outputs is generated, potentially capturing lesser known climate risks and adaptation options. Hence, ChatGPT was asked for 10 runs of the model from the same input so a set of responses could be analysed. All output was derived from pre-trained models with online retrieval enabled. This better replicates the scenario where a practitioner has limited prior knowledge or access to relevant information, or where blended

output is preferred. This set-up also provides a benchmark of the default output quality of ChatGPT.

GPT-4o was prompted in three stages—within continuous conversations—to generate sets of adaptation actions that might eventually shape a more detailed project design. Queries were deliberately kept brief but became progressively more focussed as the conversation proceeded. This was done intentionally to demonstrate how open-ended questions, without hard constraints, invite generic responses. Prompts were then sharpened at each turn (a) based on output from the previous query to (b) show the gain in detail that is achieved from more specific instructions. ChatGPT remembers previous messages in the same conversation and uses this information for context, clarification and continuity. This gives opportunities to halt misunderstandings or errors in the thread by starting a fresh conversation (Laban et al. 2025), thereby reducing the risk of error propagation, misinterpretation or overconfidence. Moreover, this approach essentially creates a tree-like human–machine reasoning process by keeping open the possibility of exploring multiple pathways, rather than generating a single answer in one step (Yao et al. 2023).

The three steps were to (1) list in descending importance the top 10 climate risks to the target receptor—whether a nation, sector or community (Level I); (2) list 10 adaptation activities for one of the risks identified in the previous step (Level II); and (3) list 10 specific adaptation measures for an illustrative activity taken from the previous step (Level III). Supplementary prompts were also used to uncover the criteria used by ChatGPT to prioritise risks and to identify potential maladaptation to climate change.

Full details of the prompts and verbatim ChatGPT responses are given in Tables S1–S5.

4 | Climate Risks and Adaptation Priorities in the United Kingdom

ChatGPT was asked to rank the 10 most important climate risks and adaptations for the United Kingdom (Table 1). This placed ‘flooding (river/coastal/urban/flash)’ as the top risk—based on the potential scale of damage and disruption, plus urgency (Table S1). All other risks returned by ChatGPT (from at least five out of 10 queries) are amongst the priorities identified by the Third Climate Change Risk Assessment (CCRA3) (Sustainability West Midlands 2021). These overlapping risks include floods, sea level rise, heatwaves, water scarcity, biodiversity loss, disruption of energy and transport systems and impacts on public health and buildings. However, there are differences in detail. The CCRA3 primary concerns also include wind and lightning, and threats to cultural heritage, whereas ChatGPT points to wildfires, water quality, widening social inequality and mental health impacts. The former do not appear in any ChatGPT output, but the latter are mentioned in the detailed explanations of the 61 risks covered by CCRA3.

ChatGPT was then asked to list ‘adaptations to flooding’ given that this was the most frequently cited risk. The Level II answers included ‘Enhance/maintain flood defences (sea walls, barriers embankments)’ (Table 1). This generic suggestion was again unpacked by prompting ChatGPT for a list of specific adaptation options to ‘enhance/maintain flood defences’. Based on the author’s experience of advising UK risk assessments, the resulting suite of measures were judged to be applicable depending on local context. Measures included Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS), smart monitoring systems, upgraded design standards to reflect climate projections and demountable defences. By running the same query 10 times, less frequent options also emerged such as use of geotextiles, tide gates and urban design (waterfront steps, floodable parks). However, there was also some double counting of actions around community flood groups and managed realignment.

For the United Kingdom, it is possible to evaluate the risks identified by ChatGPT against the eight highest priorities of the Independent Review of the CCRA3 (Climate Change Committee 2021) (Figure 3). ChatGPT returns most of the CCRA3 short list but with varying frequency (out of 10 queries) for risks to biodiversity and habitats (5); soil health (4); agriculture (7); food (2) and other (1) supply chains; transport/energy systems (7) and associated economic impacts (4); and human heat mortality (8). Some risks to the United Kingdom from climate change impacts overseas were captured by ChatGPT under insurance/financial markets (4) and disease vector spread (2). Similarly, risks to natural carbon stores are subsumed within soil degradation (1). Conversely, ChatGPT lists risks to people, property and habitats from flooding (10), water scarcity (7), sea level rise (3) and wildfires (2)—none of which were included in the high-level priorities identified by the CCC. Hence, there are marked differences in emphasis between the two sources, even though CCRA3 outputs were amongst the data used to train GPT-4o.

Even when ChatGPT is asked for the ‘top eight priorities for further climate adaptation in the next two years in the UK’—to better fit the scope of Figure 3—there are still differences (Figure 4). Soil health is not a standalone issue but is represented within ‘Agricultural adaptation’; likewise, carbon sequestration is found under ‘Biodiversity protection and ecosystem restoration’; impacts on commercial trees and from overseas are still overlooked. This raises an important question: does ChatGPT emphasise the wrong climate risks (according to the CCC)? The expert-led review certainly took a more integrated, policy domain approach to risks compared with the more siloed, hazards-based view of ChatGPT. Cross-sector thinking and integration are also evidenced by the structure of the Third National Adaptation Programme (NAP3) with chapters covering infrastructure; natural environment; health, communities and the built environment; business and industry; and international dimensions (HM Government 2023). However, it is still surprising that ChatGPT gives so much more prominence to floods and droughts than the Climate Change Committee (2021).

From this first, high-level comparison of headline messages, it may be concluded that even for well-resourced situations, ChatGPT offers a rapid, independent check of priority risks and adaptations. Although there were no surprises but some omissions within the lists generated by the LLM, perhaps value is added by more straightforward syntheses of evidence. For instance, reviewers of future CCRA3s might consider whether fundamental risks from floods, droughts, sea level rise and wildfires merit greater attention in headline messages to government and the public. Any such discrepancies might also alert to absent voices and/or risks that are being demoted in narratives for policy-makers.

5 | Climate Risk and Adaptation Priorities for Education and Training in Bangladesh

Climate change education has a crucial role to play in equipping children, young people and graduates for the challenges ahead (Monroe et al. 2019; Rousell and Cutter-Mackenzie-Knowles 2020). However, relatively little attention has been given to the potential impacts of climate change on the educational sector, including on schools, further education and Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET). Special attention is given here to TVET because it may be instrumental in developing the practical skills and knowledge needed to make economies greener (Kwauk and Casey 2022).

ChatGPT was prompted for most important climate risks and adaptations to TVET in Bangladesh (Table S2). This identified flooding, heatwaves, cyclones, salinity intrusion, air pollution and infrastructure damage as the Level I threats (Table 2). Most frequently cited priorities for adaptation involve structural, operational and curriculum-related strategies such as ‘climate-resilient infrastructure development’ and ‘integrating climate and environmental modules into TVET curricula’. Other Level II activities align well with previous recommendations (UNESCO-UNEVOC 2017)—although measures such as ‘digital and blended learning platforms’ would depend on climate-resilient energy and ITC services. The importance of ‘student stipends and retention programmes’ and ‘mobile training units’ (for improving access

TABLE 1 | Frequency (*n*) of identified climate risks and priorities for national adaptation planning (Level I) identified by ChatGPT for the United Kingdom. Activities are unpacked for ‘adaptations to flooding’ (Level II). More specific adaptation options are then requested to ‘enhance/maintain flood defences’ (Level III). See Table S1 for details about the ChatGPT conversation.

Level I: Climate risks	<i>n</i>	Level II: Adaptation to floods	<i>n</i>	Level III: Enhance/maintain flood defences	<i>n</i>
Flooding (river/coastal/urban/flash)	10	Enhance/maintain flood defences (sea walls, barriers, embankments)	10	Enhance/maintain flood defences (sea walls, barriers, embankments)	10
Heatwaves/heat-related mortality	8	Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS) in urban areas	10	Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS) in urban areas	10
Water scarcity/shortages/stress	7	Flood-resilient building and retrofit standards	9	Implement smart monitoring systems (sensors, telemetry, drones, LiDAR)	10
Agricultural stress/pests/degradation	7	Early warning systems and real-time flood monitoring	9	Raise or reinforce existing flood defences (height, strength, materials)	10
Infrastructure damage (transport/energy)	7	Restore/expand natural floodplains	9	Upgrade design standards to reflect climate projections (e.g. sea level rise)	9
Public health issues	6	Upgrade urban drainage networks and pumping stations	8	Regular maintenance schedules and structural inspections	9
Biodiversity/ecosystem loss	5	Nature-based coastal defences (managed realignment, saltmarsh)	8	Nature-based or hybrid (‘green-grey’) defences (saltmarshes, vegetated slopes)	8
Energy system vulnerability/demand shifts	5	Community flood resilience groups and public awareness campaigns	8	Modular or demountable flood barriers	7
Soil degradation/erosion/nutrient loss	4	Leaky dams and tree planting in catchments	7	Automate or retrofit major barriers (e.g. Thames) with remote/real-time operation	7
Economic impacts/inequality	4	Flood-sensitive land-use planning and zoning	7	Community involvement in defence upkeep (watch groups, local reporting)	6
Insurance/financial market risks	4	Elevated building design/flood-proof construction	6	Ensure adequate, long-term funding for defence programmes	6
Sea-level rise	3	Flood emergency response planning	5	Enable adaptive planning (managed realignment, scalable design)	6
Urban heat island effect	2	Green roofs and rain gardens	5	Embed flood defences into urban design (e.g. waterfront steps, floodable parks)	5
Food supply disruptions	2	Floodplain zoning and development restrictions	5	Training/support for local authorities and IDBs to manage local defences	4
Wildfires	2	Real-time flood modelling and forecasting tools	5	Use durable, innovative materials (self-healing concrete, corrosion-resistant alloys)	4
Disease vector spread	2	Retention ponds and buffer strips (agriculture)	4	Incorporate erosion protection (riprap, geotextiles, toe reinforcements)	3
Community displacement/migration	2	Permeable paving and infiltration trenches	4	Embed climate-risk data into defence planning tools and asset registers	3
Mental health impacts	2	Flood insurance schemes and incentives	4	Install tide gates or one-way valves to reduce backflow in estuarine/coastal areas	2
Governance/policy challenges	1	Mobile/demountable flood barriers	3	Pre-emptive repairs ahead of seasonal storms	2
Water contamination	1	Flood education and community workshops	3	Decommission or realign unsustainable defences	2
Forest degradation	1				
Supply chain disruptions	1				
Housing vulnerability	1				
Temperature extremes	1				

FIGURE 3 | Highest priorities for further adaptation in the next 2 years. Source: Climate Change Committee (2021).

FIGURE 4 | Frequency of priorities identified by ChatGPT for climate adaptation in the United Kingdom over the next 2 years (2025–2027).

TABLE 2 | As in Table 1 but for the Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Bangladesh. Adaptation activities are unpacked for ‘TVET institutions’ (Level II). More specific adaptation options are then requested to ‘enhance preparedness and minimise injury, damage and disruption during climate-related disasters’ (Level III). See Table S2 for details about the ChatGPT conversation.

Level I: Climate risks	<i>n</i>	Level II: Adaptations for TVET	<i>n</i>	Level III: Enhanced preparedness	<i>n</i>
Flooding	10	Climate-resilient infrastructure development	10	Develop and implement comprehensive disaster preparedness plans	10
Heatwaves/high temperatures	10	Integrating climate and environmental modules into TVET curricula	10	Conduct regular disaster drills and training	10
Cyclones/storms	10	Digital and blended learning platforms	9	Establish early warning systems linked to national alerts	9
Salinity intrusion/salinisation	10	Decentralised and mobile training units	8	Strengthen Infrastructure to Withstand Extreme Weather	9
Air pollution/poor air quality	10	Solar power and energy resilience solutions	8	Stockpile emergency supplies and first aid kits	8
Infrastructure damage/vulnerability	10	Early warning and emergency response systems	7	Create safe shelters within TVET campuses	8
Water scarcity/drought	9	Water harvesting and salinity management	7	Train teachers and staff in first aid and psychological support	7
Student displacement/migration	9	Student stipends and retention programmes	6	Implement digital backup systems for learning materials	7
Economic strain/poverty	9	Heat action plans and climate-sensitive timetables	6	Coordinate with local authorities and disaster response agencies	6
Curriculum gaps/lack of green skills	9	Public–private partnerships for green skill training	5	Promote student and community awareness programmes	6
Waterborne illnesses/hygiene issues	3	Climate risk mapping and institutional vulnerability assessments	3	Develop communication protocols for emergency situations	5
Respiratory health impacts	2	Teacher training in climate resilience	3	Integrate climate risk assessment in facility maintenance plans	4
Urban smog/city pollution	2	Community-based adaptation projects linked to local TVET institutions	2	Establish volunteer emergency response teams among students and staff	3
Soil salinisation	1	Mobile app development for weather and emergency alerts in TVET	2		
Unsafe drinking water	1				

by women and marginalised groups) plus ‘teacher training in climate resilience’ is also advocated elsewhere (World Bank et al. 2023). ChatGPT did not suggest using TVET facilities and local climate challenges for hands-on teaching and problem solving (i.e. using educational sites as ‘living laboratories’ [Rivera and Savage 2020]), although this possibility was identified when omitting ‘Bangladesh’ from earlier queries.

Disaster risk management (DRM) has been cited as a skills/technological gap that should be addressed by TVET (UNESCO-UNEVOC 2021). However, most attention falls on how to build capacities through curriculum development rather than by taking a more holistic approach to DRM that integrates TVET programmes, with on-site training, local industry partnerships and community engagement. The Level II options suggested by ChatGPT offer a coherent set of activities

for enhancing community resilience strategies and emergency management (Table 2). Relevant measures include ‘solar power’, ‘water harvesting’, ‘early warning and emergency response systems’, ‘heat action plans’ and ‘community-based adaptation projects’. These could be delivered via participatory community risk assessment and outreach to raise climate literacy and awareness of local hazards, as well as by developing practical and management skills needed to adapt livelihoods, local businesses and communities to climate change (Perera et al. 2017). Furthermore, TVET teachers (and their students) can play important roles in promoting and sustaining locally relevant climate-resilience skill sets and preparedness (Hasan et al. 2022).

The Level III options give more detailed suggestions to ‘enhance preparedness’ of TVET institutions (before, during and after weather extremes) (Table 2). ChatGPT proposes community

awareness campaigns, contingency planning and protocols, stockpiling, drills and asset maintenance (before); shelters on campus and emergency communication (during); plus first training staff in first aid and psychological support, recovery of information from back-up systems, volunteer teams and coordination (for post-disaster responses). Overall, the ensemble of ChatGPT responses most frequently cites activities that strengthen planning, training, infrastructure and coordination for climate-related disasters.

TVET institutions are also indispensable in ‘training community members in climate resilient livelihoods’ (Muchabaiwa and Chiweshe 2024). Hence, this phrase was used at the start of two new conversations to evaluate the ability of ChatGPT at generating a costed and justified programme of community training activities for Bangladesh (Table S3). Skill streams proposed by ChatGPT cover climate-smart agriculture, floating gardening, sustainable aquaculture, solar panel installation and maintenance and eco-tourism and green entrepreneurship for 300 unspecified participants in the first turn; or climate-smart agriculture, solar energy maintenance, sustainable aquaculture and eco-construction for 200 women, youth and marginalised farmers in the second turn. The budget of the latter is shown for illustrative purposes (Table 3). In this case, the arithmetic is correct but calculations by ChatGPT should always be checked. Follow-up queries were submitted to obtain sources of cost estimates, plus more details about the curriculum development, composition of the training team, duration of courses and potential hidden costs (e.g. training venue hire) (see Table S3). All the suggested links to (online) sources were checked—some, but not all, were contextually relevant and up to date. One source (IFAD 2024) provides credible unit costs. Overall, this example shows that ChatGPT can quickly generate a well-balanced training programme for a specified budget, but further queries are needed to elucidate important details and working assumptions behind cost estimates.

6 | Climate Adaptation Priorities for Mitigating Heatwaves in Ghana

Low-income and informal communities in the global south are on the frontline of impacts from severe storms, floods, droughts and extreme heat. This reflects their high exposure to climate-related hazards combined with poor-quality housing, fragile livelihoods, inadequate infrastructure and public services (Gough et al. 2019). Although human health risks associated with heatwaves are generally understood, surprisingly little is known about extreme heat *inside* homes, workplaces and public spaces (Wilby et al. 2021). Nonetheless, there is an urgent need to develop affordable retrofits to improve the thermal comfort, health and productivity of at-risk households. Urban Ghana was chosen as a case study because cities are expanding rapidly there and indoor temperatures can exceed 40°C. Outdoor maximum air temperatures have also increased by more than 1.0°C since the 1960s.

ChatGPT was asked for the top 10 climate risks to low-income urban communities in Ghana (Table S4). The list includes urban flooding, heatwaves and urban heat islands, water scarcity, disease outbreaks and food insecurity (Table 4). Social vulnerability to these hazards is compounded by other factors such

as poor waste management and housing, inadequate disaster preparedness and power outages. When prompted for adaptation priorities, ChatGPT most frequently refers to (1) flood protection and drainage upgrades; (2) safe and reliable water access; (3) resilient, affordable housing; (4) emergency systems and early warning; and (5) sanitation and waste infrastructure. Most of these are water related; therefore, ChatGPT was tested by asking about ‘heatwave mitigation’ for low-income homes (Table S4). All suggested options that target thermal comfort and improve resilience of the poorest in society have been reported elsewhere (Figure 5). For instance, ChatGPT suggests actions at city (e.g. green spaces), neighbourhood (e.g. cool resting areas), building (e.g. reflective materials) and human (e.g. health awareness) scales. There is also evidence of contextual insight given references to shared water points and solar-powered cooling appliances to improve resilience to frequent water-electricity outages during heatwaves (Kayaga et al. 2021). There is also a strong emphasis on using traditional building materials, shading and ventilation methods.

Level III adaptations and potential maladaptation were further explored for ‘improved ventilation systems’ (Table 4). The efficacy of many ventilation options has been evaluated before via building simulation models (e.g. Roberts et al. 2023). ChatGPT most frequently suggests (1) roof ventilation systems (vents, extractors, air gaps); (2) strategic window design for cross-ventilation; (3) openable or louvered windows/vents; (4) ventilated walls using passive airflow materials; and (5) high ceilings or vertical ventilation structures. However, it is also important to assess their social acceptability and practicality. In Ghana, known issues are fire, dust, rain and insect ingress to buildings—matters that were captured by ChatGPT (Table S4). High concentrations of dust and concerns about mosquitoes result in the widespread practice of covering up windows and louvers. High building densities and privacy and security considerations also limit the scope for re-arranging windows. Similarly, some of the measures proposed for roofs could be hampered by shortage of locally supplied traditional (thatch) materials or dust affecting reflectivity of surfaces. Nonetheless, ChatGPT provides a good account of other considerations, such as heat retention by insulation, or poor indoor air quality.

Overall, this case study demonstrates the effectiveness of ChatGPT in identifying affordable options and warnings about potential unintended negative consequences of passive ventilation and building insulation. The LLM also recognises that local communities should be engaged in the design of adaptations to address security, privacy, practicality and affordability criteria. Contextually significant concerns about dust and insects are identified by ChatGPT but not linked to occupant behaviour unless explicitly asked to do this. Then, various factors are identified (e.g. blocking windows and vents for security, use of heavy curtains and plastic sheeting and high occupancy levels). This reiterates the importance of constructing well-informed and bounded queries.

7 | Recommendations and Conclusions

This paper has taken a first look at the potential for ChatGPT to support CRAs. This LLM was used to demonstrate rapid

TABLE 3 | A programme of TVET activities to train community members in climate-resilient livelihoods in Bangladesh generated by ChatGPT. Costs are based on training duration of 5 days per participant per skill stream. There are no charges for training venue hire, as the programme delivery relies on in kind provision by local partnerships (TVET centres, NGOs).

Activity	Details	Cost per unit (\$USD)	Total units	Total cost (\$USD)
1. Curriculum development and adaptation	Customise TVET modules to local context (agriculture, solar, aquaculture etc.)	2000	1	2000
2. Trainer recruitment and training (ToT)	Train 10 local trainers from existing TVET centres	400	10	4000
3. Training delivery (four streams)	Four skills areas: climate-smart agriculture, solar tech, aquaculture, eco-friendly construction	\$100/participant	200	20,000
4. Training materials and toolkits	Manuals, seeds, toolkits, solar kits (in-kind distribution)	\$50/participant	200	10,000
5. Equipment procurement	Shared equipment for practice sites (solar panels, demo farms, toolkits)	Lump sum	1	15,000
6. Mobile training units/outreach	For remote communities (van rental, fuel, facilitators)	\$500/month	6	3000
7. Stipends/meals for trainees	Incentives for attendance (snacks, transport)	\$25/person/course	200	5000
8. Monitoring and evaluation	Baseline, midline and endline surveys, site visits	Lump sum	1	6000
9. Public awareness and graduation	Radio spots, banners, closing event, certificates	Lump sum	1	3000
10. Project coordination and admin	One part-time coordinator, travel, reporting	\$1500/month	12	18,000
11. Contingency (5%)	Unforeseen costs	-	-	4000
	Total Budget			90,000

TABLE 4 | As in Table 1 but for low-income urban communities in Ghana. Activities are unpacked for 'heatwave mitigation in low-income homes' (Level II). More specific adaptation options are then requested to 'improve ventilation systems' (Level III). See Table S4 for details about the ChatGPT conversation. Note that ChatGPT erroneously mentions cholera as a vector-borne disease (in Level I).

Level I: Climate risks	<i>n</i>	Level II: Heatwave mitigation	<i>n</i>	Level III: Improved ventilation	<i>n</i>
Urban flooding/flash floods/drain overflow	10	Roof cooling (reflective paint, insulation, white roofs, double-layering)	9	Roof ventilation (ridge vents, turbine vents, air gaps, extractors)	9
Heatwaves/rising temperatures/heat stress	9	Shade creation (trees, awnings, vines, bamboo, overhangs)	9	Cross-ventilation through window placement/design	8
Water scarcity/inadequate access to clean water	9	Passive ventilation (roof vents, cross-breeze design, open structures)	8	Use of louvered, slatted, or openable windows/vents	8
Vector-borne diseases (malaria, cholera etc.)	8	Public or shared cooling spaces (community centres, markets, shelters)	7	Ventilated wall designs (breeze blocks, perforated bricks, mesh panels)	7
Food insecurity/market disruption/price spikes	8	Heat education and awareness (flyers, health tips, campaigns)	6	High ceilings/vertical air flow (chimneys, clerestory windows, towers)	6
Coastal erosion/sea level rise/saltwater intrusion	7	Home insulation using local or recycled materials (straw, jute, cardboard)	6	Training for masons/builders in ventilation principles	6
Poor waste management/sanitation system failures	7	Hydration access (shared water, cool drinks, emergency packs)	6	Use of locally sourced breathable materials (bamboo, palm, thatch)	6
Livelihood disruption/informal economy impacts	7	Tree planting/green spaces near or around homes	6	Retrofitting homes with vents, slots, or breathable ceiling boards	5
Housing instability/informal shelter collapse	6	Community training/local builder capacity building	5	Shaded or semi-open outdoor spaces (verandas, courtyards)	5
Inadequate disaster preparedness/weak governance	5	Cool roofing materials (replacing metal/plastic sheets, adding insulation)	5	Community ventilation awareness and DIY workshops	4
Power outages/infrastructure damage	4	DIY passive cooling techniques (e.g. wet cloth, ceramic pots)	5	Orientation of homes for airflow (wind direction, room layout)	4
Respiratory and air quality health risks	4	Solar or low-energy fans and cooling devices	5	Use of recycled/upcycled materials for ventilation solutions	4
Climate-induced displacement/migration	3	Heatwave early warning systems (SMS alerts, local radio, signage)	4	Ventilation in doors (transoms, mesh doors, slatted doors)	4
Overburdened health facilities/limited access to care	3	Public participation programmes (design contests, youth involvement)	4	Airflow-enhancing internal room layouts (partial walls, open stairs)	3
Lack of urban green space/urban heat island effect	2	Cooking and activity scheduling to avoid peak heat	3	Solar or passive chimney ventilation systems	3

scoping of priority climate risks and specific adaptation options at national, sector and community scales. The tool was also asked to cost activities and to flag potential maladaptation. Other applications identified by ChatGPT (Table S5) but not covered here include development of training materials and alternative adaptation strategies. Future research could also evaluate climate risk and adaptation conversations generated by ChatGPT alongside other LLMs such as DeepSeek and Claude.

Regardless of the choice of LLM or version of ChatGPT, it is essential that we apply these assistive technologies in robust and responsible ways. Hence, the following checklist was co-developed by ChatGPT (Table S5) and the author to guide users:

1. *Define the purpose of applying the LLM* to ensure that it is not being used as a replacement for human expertise and stakeholder input.
2. *Provide very specific instructions* to bound the geographic context (point, area, place) and scope (sector, time) of the conversation.
3. *Avoid under-specified, multi-turn conversations* with LLMs to prevent error propagation and loss of reliability.
4. *Run multiple queries from identical inputs* to gauge the consistency of outputs and to pick up potentially useful minority answers.
5. *Enable online retrieval* when seeking near real-time information or content developed after the latest training period of the model.

FIGURE 5 | Pro-poor solutions to reduce exposure to heat stress in urban areas. Source: ADB (2022).

6. *Validate LLM outputs* using independent sources to sanity-check facts and figures, as well as arithmetic and technical soundness.
7. *Engage with local communities, Indigenous knowledge and data* to confirm the practical feasibility and social acceptability of identified solutions.
8. *Recognise the likely bias* in outputs due to over-representation of information from the global north in model training.
9. *Document and disclose use* of LLMs in technical reports or plans so that all sources of evidence are fully transparent and auditable.
10. *Ensure human oversight* of any decision-making that is based on content generated by LLMs.

No doubt, future advances in the architecture and training of ChatGPT will address some of the identified shortcomings. There is already the possibility of developing tools with domain-specific expertise in CRA—the various resources listed earlier in this paper would be a good place to start model training. Meanwhile, the present version showed impressive skill and could help to plug gaps in adaptive capacity, especially for vulnerable but information-scarce communities. We must always be vigilant about potential maladaptation—whether applying ChatGPT or conventional risk screening and adaptation options appraisal. The net environmental cost–benefit of using AI should be considered too.

Finally, in the words of the LLM itself: ‘ChatGPT is most valuable when used as a preliminary tool to generate ideas, support educational initiatives, assist non-specialists, and streamline the planning phase of climate adaptation. However, it should be combined with expert review, local knowledge, and detailed data analysis to ensure that the adaptation strategies are suitable and effective for specific needs’. These remarks are hard to dispute and, perhaps, a fitting way to usher in a new adaptation assistant.

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Data Availability Statement

The data sets that support the findings of this study are listed in the Supporting Information.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting Tables: cli270013-sup-0001-SupMat.docx